

This archive contains data produced in the paper "Rotation of a Ferromanganese Nodule in the Penrhyn Basin, South Pacific, Tracked by the Earth's Magnetic Field" by Oda, H., Katanoda, W., Usui, A., Murayama, M. and Yamamoto, Y. accepted to *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*.

The folder "Figure 2 Paleomagnetic Data.zip" contains paleomagnetic alternating field demagnetisation data obtained on a manganese nodule sample from Penrhyn Basin (158.39°64' W, 12°00'03' S; Water depth: 5248 m). Measurements were performed in the paleomagnetic laboratory of the Geological Survey of Japan (GSJ), AIST (a part of GSJ-Lab.). Data are in .col format with linear regression fittings on stable components, which can be read and processed using Paleomagnetism.org 2.0 (Koymans et al., 2020). "Table 1_10Be.xlsx" contains age dating results based on ¹⁰Be. "Figure 2 TimeScale" contains age model and plots based on ¹⁰Be dating in .pxp format for *Igor Pro*. It also contains a plot of Geomagnetic Polarity Time Scale in .pxp format for *Igor Pro*. The folder "Figure 2 Depth Plots.zip" contains depth plots of stable paleomagnetic components for the specimens before and after correction of growth rates. Folder "Figure 8 Rotation.zip" contains calculations related to presumed rotation of the nodule in .pxp format for *Igor Pro*. Subfolder "Great_Circle_Fitting" is the calculation of great circle fitting on series of specimens for Sample B along each line (e.g. line-a; a1, a2, b1, b2, c1, c2, d1, d2, e1 and e2). Subfolder "Rotation_Calc" is the calculation of rotation based on the poles of rotation for each great circle and a rotation angle assumed for each bottom specimen. "Table2_Rotation_Poles.xlsx" contains a pole of a great circle and a rotation angle for each line of specimens.

"Figure 3 MaxUnmix.zip" contains IRM acquisition curves obtained by VSM and the results of MaxUnmix (Maxbauer et al., 2016). Subfolder "Data" contains IRM acquisition data in excel format, whereas subfolder "MaxUnmix" contains results of MaxUnmix software in .csv format and a figure in .eps format in each specimen folder. "Figure 4 B92-1-1-A_k-o_FORC.zip" contains FORC data and FORC diagrams processed with FORCinel software in .pxp format for *Igor Pro* (Harrison and Feinberg, 2008). "Figure 6 MPMS.zip" contains results of zero field cycling measured with MPMS in .pxp format for *Igor Pro*. Subfolder "ZFcycle" is a simple plot of zero field cycling versus temperature. Subfolder "Verwey_transition_Calc" is a plot of warming curve of zero field cycling together with the calculation of Verwey transition based on the method proposed by Jackson and Moskowitz (2021). "Figure 7 Composite IRM 11.zip" contains results of composite IRM experiment on specimen 11 based on Lowrie (1990). "Figure 9 RockMag_Summary.zip" is the summary plot of rock magnetism in .pxp format for *Igor Pro*.

"Figure S1 Optical_Image.zip" contains images in TIFF format obtained with an optical scanner before and after color modifications. "Figure S1 XRF.zip" contains images on Fe, Mn and Si in TIFF format obtained with an XRF scanner at GSJ-Lab. "Figure S2 SQUIDmicroscopy" contains data and processing of S-ratio (S_{0.1T}; Bloemendal et al., 1992) measured with a scanning SQUID microscope

(SSM) at GSJ, AIST (Kawai et al., 2016; Oda et al., 2016). Subfolder “Data_before_inversion” contains vertical magnetic field values in nT obtained with the SSM on 100 micro-m grids after subtraction of reference sensor values and drift corrections. Subfolder “Sratio_Calc” contains MALAB scripts for Sratio calculation and an optical image for overlay as well as inversion results in .mat format for *MATLAB* after acquisitions of IRM (IRM_1.2T) and back field IRM at 0.1T (BIRM_-0.1T). Inversion was conducted using the method proposed by Weiss et al. (2007).

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